

METHODOLOGY FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF NATURAL SCIENCE TEACHING ORGANIZATION IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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This scientific work is relevant as a recommendation for increasing the effectiveness of lessons and awakening interest in learning among students. In the modern world, students increasingly want to learn from teachers who can teach the lesson more interestingly and using modern methods. The seemingly simple recommendations in this scientific work will significantly increase the effectiveness of lessons in universities with minimal expenditure of monetary resources on the part of the teacher [1,3].

There are various methods for increasing the effectiveness of lessons in educational institutions, but all methods are limited within two factors:

- 1) contingent (pupils of junior, middle and senior classes at school, as well as university students);
- 2) technical equipment of the audience (low, average or good).

This scientific work is aimed at a target audience of university students and “average” classroom equipment, since most educational institutions in Uzbekistan have this level of classroom equipment (with the exception of universities in which the subject “Biology” is one of the core subjects). The “medium” level of equipment includes the following: a board, a projector, a plotter, a marker or chalk, desks, chairs and an extension cord.

To increase the effectiveness of natural science lessons, three recommendations must be followed:

Compliance with cultural and ethical standards of teacher behavior in the classroom. It is recommended that the teacher lecture standing (except in cases that limit the physical capabilities of the teacher), speak clearly and in an audible voice for all students in the room, lecture with constant eye contact with students, avoid explaining topics to students with books and other aids in their hands. . The explanation of the topic should be accompanied by gestures and expressed facial

expressions. All of the above recommendations are aimed at attracting students' attention and reducing the degree of student fatigue in the classroom.

2) Application of special techniques.

Rice. 1. Epson EH-TW750 projector

Fig.2. Electronic pointer

Rice. 3. Projector board

In the classroom/office, in addition to the projector and projector boards (Fig. 1, 3), it is recommended to use electronic pointers to facilitate the teacher's activities (Fig. 2). Electronic pointers allow you to remotely switch between slides and not lose eye contact with students. The use of such gadgets during lessons shows the seriousness of preparation for the lesson, as well as the modernity of the teacher.

3) Use of various methods of questioning during lectures.

Knowledge control is an integral component of the lesson. Most university teachers do not use questioning methods during lectures, leaving this procedure for seminar classes [2]. It is recommended to use surveys during lectures using Kahoot or similar programs. In the Kahoot program, each student can connect to a survey using their

phone and answer pre-written tests and questions, and the results are displayed immediately on the screen. This survey method is based on competition among students, which increases student interest in the lesson. The survey takes 10-15 minutes from the lesson.

In conclusion, it should be noted that all of the above recommendations are

based on the high interest among students in competition and the desire to see a “modern” teacher who understands and applies modern technologies.

Thus, the methodology for increasing the efficiency of organizing the teaching of natural sciences in higher educational institutions will improve the quality of knowledge and students.

References:

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